

EFFECTS OF MICROSTRUCTURE AND OXIDATION ON FATIGUE CRACK INITIATION BEHAVIOR IN A TITANIUM ALUMINIDE ALLOY

Y. Yamazaki¹, K. Okada² & K. Yoshida²

Titanium aluminide alloys have attracted attention because of their excellent specific strength. The mechanical properties, such as fatigue strength, are sensitive to their microstructure in titanium aluminide alloys. In addition, their fatigue strength is affected by oxidation; in most cases, it degrades. This study conducted small punch fatigue (SPF) tests to investigate the effects of microstructure and oxidizing atmosphere on fatigue crack initiation behavior in a forged titanium aluminide alloy. First, the fatigue lives obtained by the SPF test were compared with the conventional uniaxial test data by means of Ni-base alloy IN718 alloy. As a result, it was confirmed that the SPF test can be applied to the fatigue test. The experimental results revealed that the microstructure significantly affected the fatigue crack initiation behavior, and the fatigue life was shorter when fatigue cracks were initiated at the lamellar phase. The thermal exposure at elevated temperatures reduced the fatigue life considerably. Such life reduction by oxidation was due to cracking the brittle oxide layer formed on the alloy surface. The fatigue strength was unaffected by the differences in thickness and kinds of oxide films formed on the specimen surface.

Keywords: Titanium aluminide alloy, Fatigue life, Microstructure, Oxidation

INTRODUCTION

The gamma-type titanium aluminide intermetallic (γ -TiAl) alloys have attracted considerable interest as a material in aircraft engines because of their superior specific strength. The 1st generation of γ -TiAl alloys developed in the 1970s had low oxidation resistance and poor ductility. Thus, the 2nd and 3rd generations of γ -TiAl alloys have been developed to improve them by adding an alloying element [1-9]. Recently, the high β -phase-containing γ -TiAl alloys with the β -Ti stabilizing elements have been attracted because of their excellent creep strength and ductility at elevated temperatures. Notably, at the temperature range between 600 and 800°C, which is almost equal to the operating gas temperature in the low-pressure turbine, LPT, section in the aero-engines, the high β -containing γ -TiAl alloys have better specific strength as compared with Ni-base superalloys. Therefore, the γ -TiAl alloys have recently been applied for an LPT blade material [10, 11]. The reduction of centrifugal force due to using the light TiAl LPT blade significantly improves the efficiency of the aero-engine because the weight of the rotor disc connecting the LPT blade can also be reduced.

The microstructure of titanium alloys, including TiAl alloys, is sensitive to heat treatment and varies to γ -phase, α -phase, α_2/γ lamella phase, etc., corresponding with the heat treatment conditions.

¹Graduate School of Engineering, Chiba University, 1-33, Yoyoicho, Inage-ku, Chiba-shi, Chiba, 263-8522 Japan, Y.yamazaki@chiba-u.jp, ² Graduate School of Science and Engineering, Chiba University, 1-33, Yoyoicho, Inage-ku, Chiba-shi, Chiba, 263-8522 Japan

It is also well known that the microstructure affects their mechanical properties, such as tensile strength, fatigue strength, etc., [12-14]. In addition, the mechanical properties of TiAl alloys are degraded by environmental attacks, such as oxidation. Therefore, the microstructure and oxidation effects on the mechanical properties should be cleared to use the TiAl alloys as structure components with higher reliability.

The small punch testing method, in which a small rigid ball punches the small disc (SD) specimen, has been applied to evaluate the ductile-brittle transition temperature of materials and to estimate the fracture toughness [15-17]. The small punch creep test has also been used to assess the creep damage of the actual components in thermal power plants [18-20]. The small punch fatigue (SPF) test was recently applied to evaluate fatigue properties [21, 22].

From the above backgrounds, the small punch fatigue (SPF) tests were conducted in this study to investigate the effects of microstructure and oxidizing atmosphere on fatigue strength in a forged TiAl alloy.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The material tested in this study is a hot-forged titanium aluminide alloy with the following chemical composition: 43% Al, 5% V, 4% Nb, and Ti balance. Three materials with different microstructures (denoted as NL-S, NL-L, and TL) were prepared by controlling the heat treatment after high-temperature forging. The microstructures of the tested materials are shown in Fig. 1. The NL-S and NL-L specimens had a near α_2/γ -lamellar microstructure. The β -grains were present along the grain boundaries of the lamellar colonies. The primary difference between both specimens was the grain size of the lamella; the lamellar sizes were 72.5 μm in the NL-S specimen and 128.3 μm in the NL-L specimen, respectively. The TL specimen had a larger content of the β -phase. The microstructure of the TL specimen consisted of α_2/γ -lamellar colonies, equiaxed γ -grains, and β -grains. The lamellar spaces within the three materials were different, i.e., the lamellar space in the NL-S and NL-L specimens (approximately 64.7nm and 77.4nm, respectively) was narrower than that in the TL specimen (approximately 161.1nm). The SD specimens were machined from the forged materials so that the $\Phi 20$ surface in each SD specimen was parallel to the forging surface. The diameter and thickness of the SD specimen are 15mm and 0.300mm (the thickness tolerance is within 0.005mm) respectively. The specimen surface was polished to mirror surface utilizing the diamond paste before the test.

In this study, the polished SD specimens were exposed under the Air, the vacuum, or the nitrogen replacement atmosphere conditions at elevated temperatures to investigate the effect of oxidation on fatigue strength. Each exposure condition is denoted as the Air-, the VO-, and the NR-condition, respectively. The nonexposed condition is denoted as the As-(polished-)condition. The exposure conditions are listed in Table 1.

In this study, the small punch fatigue (SPF) test [21, 22], which is the cyclic bending test of the SD specimen shown in Fig. 2, was also performed at room temperature with an $R = 0.1$ load ratio at a 50Hz frequency using a sinusoidal waveform. The diameter of the Si_3N_4 ceramic ball used in the SPF test was 5 mm. During the SPF test, the specimen surface was recorded by the video system with the microscope. In this study, the fatigue life of the SPF test was defined by the number of cycles at which the fatigue crack length was 300 μm , equal to the specimen thickness, was observed on the specimen surface.

TABLE 1 Exposure conditions.

Condition	Atmosphere	Temperature	Time
Air	in air	760 °C	100 min
VO	in vacuum (≈ 0.1 Pa)	760 °C	10 h
NR	in nitrogen replacement (99.99%)	970 °C	1 h

(a) NL-S

(b) NL-L

(c) TL

FIGURE 1 Microstructure of tested materials.

FIGURE 2 Schematic illustration of the SPF test [21].

In order to verify the suitability of the SPF test for fatigue life evaluation, we compared the fatigue life evaluated by the SPF test with that obtained by the conventional uniaxial fatigue (CUF) tests. The nickel base alloy, IN718, a relatively brittle material like a TiAl alloy, was used to verify the SPF test. The results of the tests, conducted under the conditions listed in Table 2, are shown in Fig. 3. It is well known that the stress is distributed along the radial direction in the specimen and decreases with the distance from the specimen center in the SPF test. Thus, for the SPF test, the circumferential stress was evaluated by the elastic finite element analysis (EFEA), and the stress

amplitude, the vertical axis in Fig. 3, was defined by that at the specimen center. The results in Fig. 3 reveal that the SPF test can be applied to assessing the fatigue lives of brittle materials since the results obtained by the SPF test were comparable to those of the CUF test.

TABLE 2 Test conditions for verification of the SPF test.

Tested material	Test temperature (°C)	Stress ratio (-)	Frequency (Hz)
IN718	Room temp.	0.1	50 Hz in SPF 5Hz in CUF

FIGURE 3 Comparison of the fatigue lives evaluated by the SPF tests and the CUF test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 4 shows the typical fatigue cracking morphology initiated and propagated on the specimen surface by the SPF test. In most cases, the almost straight crack was nucleated near the specimen center; after that, the fatigue crack was propagated with branching and kinking. Finally, three radial cracks propagated from the center macroscopically. However, as described above, note that the macroscopic morphology of the fatigue cracks was almost straight immediately after the initiation (when their length was shorter than 0.3mm).

FIGURE 4 Typical fatigue cracking morphology initiated and propagated on the specimen surface by the SPF test: NL-S specimen.

Effect of the microstructure on the fatigue strength

Figure 5 shows the SPF test results obtained in this study. As shown in Fig. 4, the fatigue crack initiation site was slightly distant from the center point of the specimen because it was affected by the microstructure. Thus, the stress amplitudes of each data shown in Fig. 5 were calculated from the circumferential stress at the initiation point for each crack based on the EFEA results. It seems from Fig. 5 that the fatigue strength of the TL specimen was relatively higher than the NL-S and NL-L specimens. However, the fatigue lives were scattered even if the same material, and thus, the effect of microstructure on the fatigue strength was unclear.

The microstructures at the initiation site for each material are shown in Fig. 6. The fatigue crack initiation morphologies were divided into two types: the fatigue crack initiated at the lamellar or the dual phase (DP) consisted of the γ - and β -phase. In addition, the fatigue lives were strongly affected by the microstructure where the fatigue crack initiated. In Fig. 4, the fatigue lives of the specimens corresponding to the fatigue crack initiated at the DP or the lamellar are shown by the open and solid symbols, respectively. As shown in Fig. 4, the fatigue strength decreased when the fatigue crack initiated from the lamellar, and the fatigue strength was almost independent of the material (i.e., the heat treatment condition after forging) if the fatigue crack initiated from the lamellar.

It is clear from Fig. 4 that the microstructure where the fatigue crack is initiated strongly affects the fatigue strength of the TiAl alloy.

FIGURE 4 Effect of microstructure on fatigue lives.

FIGURE 6 Microstructures around the fatigue crack initiation site.

Effect of oxidation on the fatigue strength

Figure 7 shows that the skinny oxidation films, less than $1\mu\text{m}$ thick, formed on the specimen surface after the Air-, VO-, and NR-conditions. On the surface of the specimen exposed under the Air- and the VO-conditions, the oxidation films consisting of aluminum and titanium oxides were formed. These oxidation films might mainly consist of the alumina and titania oxides. On the surface of the specimen exposed under NR condition, although the aluminum and titanium oxide films were also formed, the nitride concentrated layer was formed under them.

Figure 8 shows the effect of oxidation on the fatigue lives. The fatigue strength was drastically decreased by the formation of oxidation film regardless of the morphology of the formed film. It is considered that the formed oxidation films are brittle, and the cracking in the oxidation film serves as the starter notch of the fatigue crack. Therefore, the formation of the brittle oxidation film leads to the degradation of the fatigue strength. Note that the effect of microstructure on the fatigue strength becomes negligible after the oxide film formation.

It is revealed that the fatigue strength is degraded by the formation of oxidation film on the surface, and the suppression technique of oxidation film formation, such as coating one, becomes essential to improve the fatigue strength of the hot section component in aero-engine.

FIGURE 7 Results of cross sectional EDS analysis around the specimen surface of the exposed specimen.

FIGURE 8 Effect of the oxidation on the fatigue lives.

CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the effects of microstructure and oxidation on fatigue strength evaluated by the small punch fatigue test in a forged TiAl alloy.

It was confirmed by comparing the experimental results obtained by the SPF test and the conventional uniaxial test using Ni-base alloy IN718 alloy that the SPF test can be applied to the fatigue test.

The experimental results of small punch fatigue tests revealed that the fatigue life was significantly affected by the microstructure, and it was shorter when fatigue cracks initiated at the lamellar phase. The thermal exposure at elevated temperatures reduced the fatigue life considerably. Such life reduction by oxidation was attributed to cracking the brittle oxide films formed on the specimen surface. The fatigue life was unaffected by the difference in thickness and kinds of oxide films formed on the specimen surface.

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Rogers, N.J., Crofts, P.D., Jones, I.P. and Bowen, P., *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, Vols. 192-193, 1995, pp.379-386.
- (2) Larsen, D.E., *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, Vol. 213, 1996, pp.128-133.

- (3) Campbell, J.P., Ritchie, R.O., Venkateswara, Rao, K.T., *Metall. Mat. Trans. A*, Vol. 30, 1999, pp.563-577.
- (4) Roth, M. and Biermann, H., *Scr. Mater.*, Vol. 54, 2006, pp.137-141.
- (5) Roth, M. and Biermann, H., *Int. J. of Fatigue*, Vol. 30, 2008, pp.352-356.
- (6) Bauer, V. and Christ, H.-J., *Intermetallics*, Vol. 17, 2009, pp.370-377.
- (7) Heckel, T.K. and Christ, H.-J., *Procedia Engineering*, Vol. 2, 2010, pp.845-854.
- (8) El-Chaikh, A., Heckel, T.K. and Christ, H.-J., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 53, 2013, pp.26-32.
- (9) Erdely, P. Werner, R., Schwaighofer, E., Clemens, H. and Mayer, S., *Intermetallics*, Vol. 57, 2015, pp.17-24.
- (10) Bewlay, B.P., Nag, S., Suzuki, A. and Weimer, M.J., *Mat. at High Tem.*, Vol. 33, 2016, pp.549-559.
- (11) Clemens, H. and Mayer, S., *Mat. at High Tem.*, Vol. 33, 2016, pp.560-570.
- (12) Pather, P., Mitten, W.A., Holdway, P., Ubhi, H.S., Wisbey, A. and Brooks, J.W., *Intermetallics*, Vol. 11, 2003, pp.1015-1027.
- (13) Wu, X., Huang, A., Hu, D. and Loretto, M.H., *Intermetallics*, Vol. 17, 2009, pp.540-552.
- (14) Lancaster, R.J., Jeffs, S.P., Illsley, H.W., Argyrakis, C., Hurst, R.C. and Baxter, G.J., *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, Vol. 748, 2019, pp.21-29.
- (15) Dzugan, J. and Konopík, P., *J. Solid Mech.*, Vol. 6, 2012, pp. 782-791.
- (16) Wang, Z.X., Shi, H., Lu, J., Shi, P., and Ma, X.F., *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, Vol. 238, 2008, pp. 3186-3193.
- (17) Ha, J. S. and Fleury, E., *Int. J. Press. Vessel. Pip.*, Vol. 75, 1998, pp. 707-713.
- (18) Le, T.G., Yoon, K.B. and Jeong, T.M., *J. Mech. Sci. Technol.* Vol. 33, 2019, pp. 5243–5250.
- (19) Hyde, T.H., Hyde, C.J. and Sun, W., *J. Press. Vessel Technol.*, Vol. 136, 2014, pp. 1–6.
- (20) Saucedo-Muñoz, M.L., Miranda-Lopez, V., Komazaki, S. and Lopez-Hirata, V.M., *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, Vol. 761, 2019, 138033.
- (21) Yamazaki, Y., Sugaya, R., Kobayashi, U. and Ohta, U., *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, Vol. 797, 2020, 140248.
- (22) Lancaster, R.J., Jeffs, S.P., Illsley, H.W., Argyrakis, C., Hurst, R.C., and Baxter, G.J., *Materials Science & Engineering A*, Vol. 743, 2019, pp. 21-29.

